

A Study on Marketing of Coconut and Its Products in Theni and Dindigul Districts

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Abstract

In Indian, south India contributes majority of its cultivation in coconut production. In South India, Kerala state ranks first in the country for the production of coconut production and Tamil Nadu ranks number two in the country for coconut production. Coconut is the most important crop in India. In short we can say that no food can be much tastier with coconut and its product. The water of tender coconut can be used as oral rehydrate salt (ORS) during dehydration and the minerals in the tender coconut not only nourishes the body but also keeps the body cool. The study is intended to identify the socio, economic, demographic, familial profile of the coconut farmers and to analyse the marketing strategies of coconut and its products. The researcher has collected the data from coconut farmers of Theni and Dindigul districts for the study. The primary data were collected through well-structured questionnaire using convenient Sampling. The researcher has adopted convenient sampling and collected data from 250 respondents for the study during December 2018 to January 2019. The researcher has adopted percentage analysis and Chi-square test for the study. The results revealed that type of family is the only variable which is highly insignificant even though they have association with the variables. All other variables are found to be highly significant.

Keywords: Coconut, cultivation, yield, growth, production, marketing channel, sale.

Introduction

"Agricultural marketing as a process which starts with a decision to produce a saleable farm commodity and it involves all aspects of market structure of system, both functional and institutional, based on technical and economic considerations and includes pre and post-harvest operations, assembling, grading, storage, transportation and distribution" - The National Commission on Agriculture (1976).

The Coconuts were marketed in three types (i) Fresh Coconut, (ii) Copra (iii) Coconut oil and (iv) Dry Coconut. Coconut plantation was first originated from South East Asia. Coconut is grown in more than eighty countries in the world. The country namely Indonesia and Philippines ranks first and second in the world for the production of coconut. India ranks third in the world in the production of coconut products by planting coconut in 1.78 hectares as a crop, it produces more than 7562

million nuts and breeds more than 5295 nuts per hectare (Shashikumar.S and Chandrasekar, 2014). In Indian, south India contributes majority of its cultivation in coconut production. In South India, Kerala state ranks first in the country for the production of coconut and Tamil Nadu ranks number two in the country for coconut production. South India fulfils 90 percent of coconut production of the country (Bhoopathy.G, 2016). In South India, four major districts that contribute for its coconut production are Coimbatore, Thanjavur, Dindigul and Theni. The coconut crop cultivators in Theni district cultivate and yield the nut coconut and sell their products directly to the customers in whole sale or by retail. They also provide sales to the dealers. The Coconut cultivator gets their support from both private and public agencies like Reliance Foundation, Kalpavrisa Parachute, Coconut Board of India etc. The banks like Canara Bank, NABARD bank, Co-operative bank fulfils the loan requirements of the coconut farmers. The Marketing of coconut products is more challengeable job. The farmers were affected by GAJA cyclone since 10 November 2018. Most of the coconut trees were affected by the cyclone. Government has subsidised Rs 1100/- per tree which is not sufficient to farmers. Hence the production of coconut is affected and increased the price of Coconut.

Benefits of Coconut and its Products

Coconut is the most important crop in India. In short we can say that no food can be much tastier with coconut and its product. The water of tender coconut can be used as oral rehydrate salt (ORS) during dehydration and the minerals in the tender coconut not only nourishes the body but also keeps the body cool. The coconut oil can be used for applying it in the head for better hair growth; it can be also used as coolant. The coconut oil contributes majority of its benefits in Siddha, Ayurveda and Naturopathy medicines. The coconut milk and coconut mixture is used as the taste enhancer in food. The coconut sweets are good for health and it also helps in digestion. It increases the economic growth of the farmers. Coconut and its products have many more benefits.

Review of Literature

Abankwah.V, Aidoo. R and Tweneboah-Koduah (2010), has studied “Margins and economic viability of fresh coconut marketing in the Kumasi metropolis of Ghana”. In their study they analysed the magnitude of margins between producer and marketers along the distribution channel viability of fresh coconut marketing. The study was conducted in Roman Hill, Suame Roundabout, Asafo, Sofo line, Bantama, Aboabo, Ahodwo, Atonsu, Kurofoforomu, Kwadaso, Asawasi, and Akwatialine markets and retailing of fresh coconut in the Kumasi metropolis. The study revealed that there was no equitable distribution of income along the distribution channel as required by economic goal. Fresh coconuts are priced exorbitantly at wholesale and retail levels, thereby making abnormal profit with a profitability being several times more than the going interest rate in the economy. Tine rant wholesalers turned over their capital 24 times within a year. Retailers who realized the highest profitability were found to have turned over the working capital 52 times in a year.

Kumar and Sanjeev Kapoor (2010), has undergone the study titled “Value Chain Analysis of Coconut in Orissa”. They examined the market chains for coconut to find the flow of product from farmers through different intermediaries to the consumers. They conducted the study in five coastal districts of Orissa, namely, Puri, Cuttack, Khurda, Ganjam, and Jagatsinghpur. The study revealed that vendors use different channels to market nuts. These included self-selling to consumers, selling to large vendors, and selling to aggregators. Aggregators too had multiple options. Some aggregators were found importing coconut to meet the market demand from within or outside the state. It indicates that the entire demand of marketing channel in the state was not being met by internal production.

Mwachiro E. C and Gakure.R.W, (2011), has conducted the study “Factors Affecting the Coconut Industry from Benefitting the Indigenous Communities of Kilifi District, Kenya”, the factors hindering the local community from benefiting from this cash crop. The study was conducted at three selected sites, namely Mtwapa on the southern border of Kilifi district near Mombasa, Tezo/Roka. They collected the data through well-structured questionnaire from 150 framers by simple random sampling technique. The results indicated that low prices of the coconut products, unclear legal framework, lack of proper markets, poor farming methods, low productivity and lack of financial support from the government and financial institutions are some of the factors that hinder the indigenous community from benefiting from the coconut products in the region.

Bhoopathy.G, (2016), investigated the study titled “A Study on Marketing Problems of Coconut with Special Reference to Coimbatore District” in his study he identified the satisfaction level of respondents regarding the support provided by the Coconut Development Board. He also analysed the problems faced by the respondents and its causes. He has collected the data from all over Coimbatore district by drafting well-structured questionnaire and was distributed over 200 respondents by convenient sampling. The results revealed that the opinion of the respondents are positively correlated in expressing their view regarding the experience in cultivation, type of manure used, type of irrigation followed by the respondents and mode of selling the coconut cultivated by the respondents.

Dhara.R, Umamageswari.M and Porchezhiyan.S (2016), has undergone study “Marketing problems encountered by coconut growers in Thanjavur district of Tamil Nadu”. In their study they have tried to find out the constraints encountered by the coconut growers in coconut cultivation. The study was conducted in two taluks of Thanjavur districts in Tamil Nadu to elucidate the constraints of coconut growers in marketing of their produce. Sample of 120 coconuts were selected randomly from selected taluks of the districts and the information was collected through structured interview schedule. The study found that the Lack of exclusive market for coconut, lack of co-operative marketing system, scarcity of labour for transportation and marketing and lack of market information were the problems in marketing of coconut. Fluctuation in market price was the major trading constraints whereas, it was lack of availability of long term credit in financial aspects and lack of village level co-ordination was the major physical constraints.

Padma.D and Kothai Andal.C (2016), has conducted the study titled “A study on Awareness of coconut cultivators on value added products in Coimbatore District”. In their study they tried to find out the demographic profile of the coconut cultivators, identifying the awareness level on value added products. They have collected the data from all over Coimbatore district by drafting well-structured questionnaire and were distributed over 200 respondents by convenient sampling. The results revealed that the percentage of the respondents with high level of awareness is found high among the respondents with less than 5 years of experience in coconut cultivation. The percentage of respondents with low level of awareness is found high among the respondents whose experience is 5-10 years of experience. It can be inferred that the level of awareness is found high among the respondents with less than 5 years of experience.

Yamuna.S.M, and Ramya.R (2016), has investigated the study titled “A Study of Coconut Cultivation and Marketing in Pollachi Taluk”. In their study they examined the awareness of respondents about the coconut marketing and also analysed the problems in coconut cultivation and marketing. They have collected the data from all over Coimbatore district by drafting well-structured questionnaire and were distributed over 250 respondents by convenient sampling. The results revealed that there is a significant association between the number of farming land possessed by the respondents and the areas of coconut seedlings planted by the respondents. There is a significant association between the acres of farming land possessed and the type of subsidy received by the respondents.

Ine Fausayana, Weka Gusmiarty Abdullah, La Ode Dawid, (2018), has conducted the study titled “Risk Analysis of Coconut Product Marketing”, They have tried to analysis the risks of coconut products marketing in Kendari City. This study was conducted in Kendari City, South East Sulawesi, Indonesia. Kendari City is the capital of Southeast Sulawesi Province (Sultra) with the function as the centre of economic circulation and government. The results of this study described the risk identification in three stage of marketing of coconut product, namely (a) Five risks identified at the stage of storing; broken coconut fruit, unsold product, fire market, theft of coconut fruits, and market regulation; (b) Three risks identified at the stage of processing; broken coconut, coconut shell waste, and damage to processing facilities; and (c) Four risks identified at the stage of selling; unsold product, non-strategic selling locations, substitute goods, and competitors.

Objectives of the Study

1. To identify the socio, economic, demographic, familial profile of the coconut farmers.
2. To analyse the marketing strategies of coconut and its products.

Scope of the Study

This study attempts to find out the socio, economic, demographic and familial profile of the coconut farmers and to analyse the marketing strategies of coconut and its products.

Research Methodology

Profile area of the study

The researcher has collected the data from coconut farmers of Theni and Dindigul districts for the study.

Source of Data Collection

The primary data were collected through well-structured questionnaire using convenient Sampling.

Sample Size and Sample Design

The researcher has adopted convenient sampling and collected data from 250 respondents for the study during December 2018 to January 2019.

Tools for Data Collection

The researcher has adopted percentage analysis and Chi-square test for the study

Limitations of the Study

1. The study was confined and limited to Theni and Dindigul Districts only due to time limitations.
2. The study was done based on pure primary data. The recording over the data is true as per the representation given by the respondents only. Some of them were in hurry and gave the data as per compulsion.
3. The data were collected from those farmers those who are willing to provide the data for research purpose.

Background Profile of the Respondents

Demographic Profile

From the table 01 it is clear that most of the respondents (40 percent) belongs to the age group of 31 to 40 years followed by the age group of 41 to 50 years and 50 years and above with 30 and 18 percent respectively. It is also clear that majority of respondents are male followed by female with 70 and 30 percent respectively.

Table 1 Demographic Profile

(N= 250)

Demographic Profile	Number of Respondents
Age	
21 to 30 years	30 (12)
31 to 40 years	100 (40)
41 to 50 years	75 (30)
Above 50 years	45 (18)
Gender	
Male	175 (70)
Female	75 (30)

Source: Compiled from the field data (2018-19)

Note: Figures in parantheses are percentage to the coloum total.

Social profile

From the below table it is clear that most of the respondents belongs to backward caste with 64 percent, followed by SC/ST and Most Backward Caste with 16 and 12 percent. As per religion most of the respondent belongs to Hindu religion with 78 percent followed by Christian and Muslim with 16 and 6 percent. Most of the respondents belong to rural area with 80 percent followed by semi urban and urban area with 16 and 4 percent respectively.

Table 2 Social Profile of the Respondents

(N=250)

Social Profile	Number of Respondents
Caste	
Forward Caste	20 (08.0)
Backward Caste	160 (64)
Most Backward Caste	30 (12)
Scheduled Caste/ Scheduled Tribe	40 (16)
Religion	
Hindu	195 (78)
Christians	40 (16)
Muslims	15 (06)
Residential Status	
Urban area	10 (04)
Semi Urban area	40 (16)
Rural area	200 (80)

Source: Compiled from the field data (2018-19)

Note: Figures in parantheses are percentage to the coloum total.

Familial Profile

As per the Table 03 it is clear that most of the respondents are married with 90 percent and remaining are unmarried with 10 percent. Most of the respondents live in joint family with 72 percent and remaining in nuclear family with 28 percent. Most of the respondents have four members with 72 percent followed by five members and more than six members with 16 and 7.2 percent respectively. It is also clear that maximum numbers of earning members in the family are two with 60 percent followed by more than four members and three members with 20 and 16 percent respectively.

Table 3 Familial Profile of the respondents

(N=250)

Familial Profile	Number of respondents
Marital Status	
Married	225 (90)
Unmarried	25 (10)
Type of the Family	
Joint family	180 (72)
Nuclear family	70 (28)
Size of the Family	
Two members	02 (0.8)
Three members	10 (04)
Four members	180 (72)
Five members	40 (16)
More than six members	18 (7.2)
Number of Earning Family Members	
One members	20 (08)
Two members	150 (60)
Three members	30 (12)
More than four members	50 (20)

Source: Compiled from the field data (2018-19)

Note: Figures in parantheses are percentage to the coloum total.

Economic Profile

It is clear from the below table that most of the respondents earn Rs 2 Lakhs and above as their annual income with 64 percent followed by their annual income Rs 1,00,000 to 1,50,000 16 percent, Rs 50,000 to 1,00,000 and Rs 1,50,000 to 2,00,000 with 8 percent each. It is also clear that most of the respondents spends their annual expenditure about Rs 75,000 to 1,00,000 (64 percent). Followed by Rs 50,000 to 75,000 (16 percent), Rs 25,000 to 50,000 and Rs 1,00,000 and above with 8 percent each.

Table 4 Economic Profile of the Respondents

(N=250)

Economic Profile	Number of Respondents
Annual Income in Rupees	
Below 50,000	10 (04)
50,000 to 1,00,000	20 (08)
1,00,000 to 1,50,000	40 (16)
1,50,000 to 2,00,000	20 (08)
2,00,000 and above	160 (64)
Annual Expenditure in Rupees	
up to 25,000	10 (04)
25,000 to 50,000	20 (08)
50,000 to 75,000	40 (16)
75,000 to 1,00,000	160 (64)
1,00,000 and above	20 (08)

Source: Compiled from the field data (2018-19)

Note: Figures in parantheses are percentage to the coloum total.

Educational Profile

It is clear from the table below that most of the respondents have no formal education with 60 percentage followed by the respondents with education up to graduation and SSLC with 16 and 12 percent respectively.

Table 5 Educational Profile of the Respondents

(N=250)

Educational Profile	Number of Respondents
Unmarried Status	NA
No formal education	150 (60)
up to Secondary	30 (12)
Higher Secondary	10 (04)
Diploma	20 (08)
Graduate	40 (16)
Post Graduate	0
Professional Degree	0

Source: Compiled from the field data (2018-19)

Note: Figures in parentheses are percentage to the column total.

Marketing of Coconut and its products

Table 6 Association of Marketing of Coconut and Its Products

Variables	Chi-square Value	Level of Significance
Age	170.291	0.000
Gender	35.998	0.021

Caste	98.265	0.000
Religion	108.322	0.000
Marital Status	55.337	0.000
Type of family	17.185	0.649
Number of family members	126.467	0.000
Number of earning family members	348.308	0.000
Residential Status	105.877	0.000
Annual Income	242.167	0.000
Annual Expenditure	198.512	0.000
Education of the respondent	455.586	0.000
Occupation of the respondent	238.737	0.000

H- There is no significant association between Background variables and the marketing of coconut and its products.

H1- There is significant association between Background variables and the marketing of coconut and its products.

From the above table type of family is the only variable which is highly insignificant (0.649) even though they association with the variables. Gender is the only variable which is found to significant at 5 percent. All other variables are found to be highly significant. Hence null hypothesis is rejected.

Conclusion

From the above study it is clear that the even though the marketing of coconut and its products are performing well there is still requirement of concentrating on the marketing strategies. There is a need in the improvement of marketing channels for better improvement and better yield. If the yield is increased then the marketing of coconut will be increased. But the high price of coconut is the most affecting factor in the market. There is the requirement to reduce the cost of coconut which can even serve better even to the public.

References

1. Shashikumar.S and Chandrasekar, (2014), "An Analysis of Production and Marketing of Coconut in Tumkur District, India", International Journal of Current Research and Academic Review, ISSN: 2347-3215, Vol.2 (10), pp-167-165.
2. Bhoopathy.G, (2016), "A Study on Marketing Problems of Coconut with Special Reference to Coimbatore District", International Journal of Engineering Research and Modern Education (IJERME), ISSN (online): 2455-4200, Vol.1 (02), pp-59-70.
3. Abankwah.V, Aidoo.R and Tweneboah-Koduah (2010), "Margins and economic viability of fresh coconut marketing in the Kumasi metropolis of Ghana", Journal of Development and Agricultural Economics, ISSN 2006- 9774 Vol. 2(12), pp- 432-440.
4. Niraj Kumar and Sanjeev Kapoor (2010), "Value Chain Analysis of Coconut in Orissa", Agricultural Economics Research Review, Vol. 23, pp 411-418.
5. Mwachiro E. C and Gakure.R.W, (2011), "Factors Affecting the Coconut Industry from Benefitting the Indigenous Communities of Kilifi District, Kenya", International Journal of Humanities and Social Science, Vol. 1 (4), pp-214- 230.

6. Dhara.R, Umamageswari.M and Porchezhiyan.S (2016), “Marketing problems encountered by coconut growers in Thanjavur district of Tamil Nadu”, Advance Research Journal of Social Science, ISSN 2231–6418, Vol. 7 (1), pp-51- 54.
7. Padma. D and Kothai Andal.C (2016), “A study on Awareness of coconut cultivators on value added products in Coimbatore District”, International Journal of Advance Research in Computer Science and Management Studies, ISSN (Online)- 2321-7782, Vol.4(3), pp.55-60.
8. Yamuna.S.M, and Ramya.R (2016), “A Study of Coconut Cultivation and Marketing in Pollachi Taluk”, International Journal of Innovative Research in Management Studies (IJIRMS), ISSN (Online): 2455-7188, Vol.1 (2), pp - 77-98.
9. Ine Fausayana, Weka Gusmiarty Abdullah, La Ode Dawid, (2018), “ Risk Analysis of Coconut Product Marketing”, International Journal of Research Granthaalayah, ISSN (O)- 2350-0530, ISSN (P)- 2394-3629, Vol.6(5), pp. 1138-148.